

Potential Fungicidal Compounds. Part II. Some Bis-halogeno-nitrophenyl and -naphthyl Esters of Piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamic Acid

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A few bis-halogenonitrophenyl esters of piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamic acid have been obtained by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzenes and sodium piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamate with a view to studying their fungicidal and insecticidal activity. Structures to these compounds have also been assigned.

Halogenonitrophenyl and -naphthyl esters of *N*-substituted dithiocarbamic acids have been found to possess fungicidal activity¹. These have also been used as accelerators in rubber vulcanization². The work¹ is now extended to the synthesis of some bis-halogenonitrophenyl and -naphthyl esters of piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamic acid with a view to studying their fungicidal and insecticidal activity.

The esters have been obtained by the condensation of halogenonitrobenzenes with sodium piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamate in ethanolic solution. By the condensation of 1,2,5-trichloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene with sodium piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamate, two isomeric compounds, bis-3,6-dichloro-2,4-dinitrophenyl- and bis-4,5-dichloro-2,6-dinitrophenyl esters of piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamic acid could possibly result; but only one compound could, however, be isolated. Identical compound, as found by the determination of melting point, is obtained by condensing sodium piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamate with 2,5-dichloro-1-bromo-4,6-dinitrobenzene. Both of them therefore must be bis-3,6-dichloro-2,4-dinitrophenyl ester of piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamic acid and the halogen in position 1 is involved in the condensation. Similarly, 1,2,5-tribromo- and 1-chloro-2,5-dibromo-4,6-dinitrobenzenes provide bis-3,6-dibromo-2,4-dinitrophenyl ester of piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamic acid.

The structure to the esters, obtained from 1,2,3-trihalogeno-4,6-dinitrobenzenes is based on our previous observation¹. Fungicidal and insecticidal activities of these compounds are under investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium Piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamate.—A solution of piperizine hexahydrate (11g.) in ethanol (30 ml) was added with stirring to a well-cooled (10-15°) solution of NaOH

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1. Garg, *This Journal*, 1965, 42, 339, 415.

2. Cadwell, U. S. P., 1726646; *Chem. Abs.*, 1929, 23, 5353.

TABLE I

Halogenonitrophenyl and -naphthyl esters of piperazine-bis-dithiocarbamic acid.

Halogenonitrobenzenes.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Recd.	%Sulphur. Found. Recd.
1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-	230° d	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₂ NS ₄	14.69	14.74
1,2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	210-12° d	C ₁₀ H ₂ O ₂ NS ₄ Cl ₂	13.01	13.15
1-Chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-	112°	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₂ NS ₄ Br	11.49	11.54
1-Chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitro-	233d°	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₂ NS ₄ I	10.13	10.23
1,2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	272d°	C ₁₀ H ₂ O ₂ NS ₄ Cl ₂	13.20	13.15
1,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro-	182d°	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₂ NS ₄ Cl ₂	13.09	13.15
1,4-Dibromo-2,6-dinitro-	236-36° d	C ₁₀ H ₂ O ₂ NS ₄ Br ₂	11.51	11.54
1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-	227° d	C ₁₁ H ₆ O ₂ NS ₄	13.90	14.05
1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-	205°	C ₁₁ H ₆ O ₂ NS ₄	13.99	14.05
1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methyl-	196°	C ₁₁ H ₆ O ₂ NS ₄	14.00	14.05
1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-	168°	C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₂ N ₃ S ₄	16.01	16.26
1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro-	190°	C ₁₀ H ₂ O ₂ NS ₄ Cl ₃	11.79	11.96
2-Chloro-1,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-	225° d	C ₁₀ H ₂ O ₂ NS ₄ Br ₂ Cl	10.46	10.54
1,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-	203° d	C ₁₁ H ₆ O ₂ NS ₄ Cl ₂	12.33	12.59
1,2,5-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro-	192-3°	C ₁₀ H ₂ O ₂ NS ₄ Cl ₃	11.90	11.96
2,6-Dichloro-1-bromo-4,6-dinitro-	192-3°	C ₁₀ H ₂ O ₂ NS ₄ Cl ₂ Br	11.03	11.96
1,2,6-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro-	211° d	C ₁₀ H ₂ O ₂ NS ₄ Cl ₃	9.51	9.48
1-Chloro-2,5-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-	211° d	C ₁₀ H ₂ O ₂ NS ₄ Br ₂ Cl	9.08	9.48
1-Chloro-2,4-dinitro-naphthalene	216-17° d	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₂ NS ₄	12.34	12.53

*All melting points are uncorrected.

N.B. d denotes decomposition. NP denotes nitrophenyl.

(8.5g.) in water (8 ml) and ethanol (20 ml). The resulting mixture was cooled (5-6°) and CS_2 (15 g.) was added (90 min.) dropwise with vigorous stirring. The stirring was continued for another hour and the temperature was maintained below 10°. The crystals separating were filtered and recrystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. > 300° (decomp.). (Found: S, 44.98. Calc. for $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{S}_4\text{Na}_2$: S, 45.39%).

Bis-phenyl Esters of Piperizino-bis-dithiocarbamic Acid.—A 20% solution of reactive halogenonitrobenzene (0.2M) in ethanol was added dropwise to a 15% solution of the preceding ester (0.01M) with stirring during 45 min., the temperature being maintained at 0°-2°. The mixture was well stirred (below 5°) till the product separated. It was washed, dried, and crystallised from acetone. The esters are generally yellow crystalline compounds, insoluble in water. Their melting points, yields, and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

The authors are thankful to Meerut College authorities for providing necessary facilities and to the State Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (U.P.) for contingency grant to one of them (S. P. G.).

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Received January 29, 1965.